

100+ YEARS OF PATENTING IN SERBIA

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Abstract: *The paper analyses patenting in Serbia from the establishment of the Office for the Protection of Industrial Property of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia in 1921 to 2023. In a period of 102 years, domestic inventors were exposed to major political changes, wars, changes in the economic system and conditions for inventive work. For foreign inventors, the market in Serbia was a challenge to conquer, in which one of the first instruments was patent protection. The long time series of data on domestic and foreign patent applications represents a rich information fund for the analysis of one of the most important indicators of the functioning of the national innovation system. One of the conclusions that imposes itself on the author is that Serbia, after 102 years of patent activity, is somewhere again at the beginning of the path to the development of the economy based on its own knowledge and technologies.*

Keywords: *Patent activity, Serbia, Longitudinal research.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Patent statistics are one of the very few measurable indicators of research and development activities aimed at potential market exploitation. Moreover, patent activity is still a phase that precedes the development of innovations offered on the market of goods and services. Namely, many patents will never reach that phase of the innovation cycle, and some patents can be used to develop multiple innovations (so-called "generic" patents). Therefore, in the literature, authors have reached a consensus that patent statistics are important, but imperfect indicator of innovative activities (Pavitt, 1988; Griliches, 1990). Also, the literature proves that the number of patented inventions provides a fairly good, although not perfect, representation of innovative activity, thus supporting the use of the number of patents in studies examining technological change (Acs et al, 2002). Furthermore, a methodology is given that combines patent content clustering and technology life cycle forecasting to find a niche in the industry, as part of technology forecasting research (Trappey et al, 2011), that is, a model is developed to facilitate governments, inventors and manufacturing organizations to identify new research directions, which includes steps such as knowledge extraction on patents, presentation of knowledge and identification of research trends (Abbas et al, 2014)

Given the importance that patents can have for the development of new and/or improved products and services, and for innovation activity as a whole in general, the likelihood of success in directing patent activity towards the market realization of innovations largely depends on the model of scientific research and development (R&D) work that is represented in an economy, that is, the model on which the management and financing of research and innovation in a country depends. The classification of models and a broader discussion of their application in the governance of the research and innovation in Serbia is given in the author's article [Kutlača, 2022], which also provides a chronology of the development of innovation policies: (1) The first generation of innovation policy is based on the so-called "linear model of innovation activities", starting from basic sciences and moving in successive phases until new knowledge is incorporated into applications acceptable for market valorisation; (2) The second generation of innovation policy is based on the so-called "chain model", which characterizes feedback loops between different phases of the innovation process [Klein and Rosenberg, 1986]; (3) The third generation of innovation policy places innovation activities as a key area of every policy and represents the so-called "innovation activities integration model".

The evolution of innovation policies from a linear model, through a chain model, has led to a model of integration of innovation activities. The chain model is particularly important because of the feedback loops, which, in a theoretical sense, it has led to the concept of national, regional, sectoral and other types of innovation systems [Freeman 1987]. According to this model, innovation policy aims to improve two-way communication between different actors in the chain of the innovation activities and improve all types of innovation systems in order to ensure the establishment of an information-based decision-making system, i.e., to inform decision-makers on research and development, commercialization, adoption and implementation of technology, etc. It can be said that this model is still dominant in the organization of public governance of research and development and other innovation activities, and the third generation of innovation policies manages the networking process between all actors in the *national innovation system* (NIS). Innovation can be considered as the result of a learning process, which is interactive and cumulative in nature. Interactions within the economy, which may result in the combination of existing knowledge or, in some cases, new knowledge, take place between companies, financial, educational, research and development and other organizations, government agencies and other public and/or private institutions [Galli and Teubal, 1997]. Technological development is the result of complex interactions between the aforementioned organizations, which Richard Nelson first called the “*capitalist engine of growth*” [according to: Albuquerque, 1997], and later the “*national innovation system*” (NIS) [Nelson, 1993]. The NIS scheme is given in Figure 1, according to the modified concept of the author S. Kuhlmann [Kuhlmann, 2003].

Figure 1: NIS – Concept modified and extended by S. Kuhlmann [Kuhlmann, 2003]

Research on the governance of science and technology development indicates the subject of interest of the relevant ministries in building a national innovation system. Thus, four key areas of management actions in the EU member states have been identified [Kuhlmann, 2003]: (1) In the 1970s, research and development (R&D) activities were stimulated as the main objective and main priority of innovation policy (IP). Subsidies

for R&D work were the content of IP, and financing was the main instrument of IP, both in the member states and at the level of the European Union; (2) In the 1980s, the transfer of knowledge and/or technological competence was stimulated as a priority and main objective, and research and development activities were stimulated as the content of innovation policy. The main instrument of EU innovation policy was support for the diffusion of knowledge and technologies; (3) In the 1980s, support for business start-ups was stimulated as the main objective of innovation policy. Social sciences, formal and tacit knowledge were the priorities and content of IP. The main instrument of EU innovation policy was support for management in research and development; (4) Since the late 1990s, and continuing to this day, facilitating change has been promoted as a priority of EU innovation policy. The content of innovation policy consists of scientific areas, formal and tacit knowledge, as well as the provision of strategic information, necessary for both current innovation activities and planning for future ones. System instruments are the main instruments of IP, e.g., supporting and reorganizing innovation networks, providing initiatives for organizational change and for the implementation of activities for predicting NT development ("foresight" in science and technology).

This introduction, which outlines the evolution of innovation policies, with the main elements of the governance mechanisms of administrations responsible for research and innovation, aims to highlight the importance that science and innovation governance has on the scientific research community and potential inventors and innovators. The results or consequences of science and innovation governance in a country are best illustrated by two sets of indicators: (1) Indicators of publication of papers in journals registered in the WoS and Scopus databases; (2) Indicators of intellectual property protection, especially patents, in national intellectual property offices, as well as in three specific offices: the European Patent Office (EPO), the US Patent Office (USPTO) and the Japanese Patent Office (JPO). The bottom of Figure 1 illustrates the infrastructure for NIS, without which NIS cannot be formed and function. One of the elements of this infrastructure is intellectual property rights (IPR). It is precisely the knowledge codified in patent documentation that represents a resource for further development into marketable products/processes/services, which must be available to all NIS actors. Reform of legislation in the field of intellectual property rights (IPR) in order to harmonize with EU standards in the countries of Central and Eastern Europe is an integral part of transitional changes [WDR, 1996] and one of the indicators of success in the implementation of negotiation chapters in the EU accession process (Chapter 7: Intellectual property law) in a particular country [EC, 2024]. Harmonization of legislation in the field of IPR with EU standards is one of the main conditions for the entry of foreign direct investment, because before entering the market of a country, foreign companies first protect their patents and other intellectual property rights, and only then bring their technologies, processes and products. Again, through the indicators of patent activity in a country, governance mechanisms for supporting research and innovation can be analysed, because these indicators indicate the interest of foreign inventors in the protection of IPR in a country. It has been shown in the literature that the number of patents protected by non-residents of a country in the countries of Central and Eastern Europe from 1945 to 1989 was marginal, to some extent with the exception of the former Yugoslavia [Radošević and Kutlaca, 1998]. It singles out a set of IPR indicators as a result of research and innovation for the subject of this paper.

The paper analyses patenting in Serbia from the establishment of the Office for the Protection of Industrial Property of the Kingdom of Serbia in 1921 to 2023. In a period of 102 years, domestic inventors were exposed to major political changes, wars, changes in the economic system and conditions for inventive work. For foreign inventors, in some periods the Serbian market was a challenge to conquer, in which one of the first instruments was patent protection. The long time series of data on domestic and foreign patent applications represents a rich information fund for the analysis of one of the most important indicators of the functioning of the NIS. The analysis itself aims to indicate the effects of the governance mechanisms that the responsible administrations established in that period to support R&I. At the end of this extensive introduction, one of the conclusions that imposes itself on the author is that after 102 years of patent activity, Serbia is once again at the beginning of the path to economic development based on its own knowledge and technologies.

2. PATENTING IN SERBIA

In a paper from 1998, the author analyses the influence and effects of the decisions of the responsible administration on patenting in Serbia from 1921 to 1995 [Kutlaca, 1998]. This paper extends the time series of data on patent applications by residents and non-residents in Serbia until 2023. The concluding remarks comment on the governance of research and innovation in Serbia in the last three decades of patenting activity.

2.1. Patent applications of domestic authors

The Kingdom of Serbia is one of the signatory states - founders of the Paris Convention on the Protection of Industrial Property on March 20, 1883, together with Belgium, France, Italy and the Netherlands. Great Britain acceded to the Convention in 1884, the USA in 1887, and Germany in 1903. The Kingdom of Yugoslavia inherited the status of Serbia and acceded to the Convention in 1921. The Paris Convention on the Protection of Industrial Property from 1883 is still a valid regulation and standard for relations between countries in the field of intellectual property protection.

Figure 2: The patenting of domestic authors from Serbia in the observed period, from 1921 to 2023

Having established an adequate relationship with the ownership of intellectual property, Serbia developed its capitalist economy at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century by encouraging inventive work, formal protection of intellectual property rights, and then continued innovative activities aimed at the development of products, processes and services. Figure 2 illustrates the patenting of domestic authors from Serbia in the entire observed period, from 1921 to 2023. *The patent activity of domestic inventors* grew from 1921 until the beginning of the WW2. After the end of the war, greater involvement of inventors begins again, and reaches its culmination in the period from 1971 to 1991. War events in the former Yugoslavia drastically reduced the number of patent applications by domestic authors, with a slight halt in the decline in that number in the period from 2001 to 2010. Then there is a decline and stagnation again, only to drop drastically again with the corona virus epidemic. At the end of the observed period of 103 years, shortly before the epidemic, the intensity of patenting was at the level reached before the WW2.

2.2. Patent applications of foreign authors

The conditions for the protection of intellectual property in the Kingdom of Yugoslavia represented an acceptable environment for foreign companies and inventors, which brought their technologies to Yugoslavia / Serbia with prior protection in the Office for the Protection of Industrial Property of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia. By the beginning of WWII, the number of patent applications by both domestic and foreign authors reached a respectable level, and the protected technologies were the driver of the country's industrialization and a source of knowledge for the educated population. Figure 3 illustrates the patenting of foreign authors in the entire observed period, from 1921 to 2023.

Figure 3: The patenting of foreign authors in the observed period, from 1921 to 2023

After WW2, *foreign authors* applied for more and more patents, and significant growth was recorded in the period from 1971 to 1985, similar to the case of domestic inventors. It is indicative, however, that the decline in the number of applications by foreign authors began a few years before the beginning of the disintegration of the former Yugoslavia, because the deterioration of the political situation in Yugoslavia had the effect of reducing the interest of foreigners in entering that market. The relative increase in the interest of foreign inventors in patent protection in Serbia can be seen again in the period from 2001 to 2017, and then a drastic drop in the number of patent applications by foreign authors begins. The growth of the economy that is said to be happening after the corona virus epidemic is obviously not based on technologies that need protection, that is, it is driven by labour-intensive technologies that were launched (and protected) on the market many years ago. Obviously, foreign inventors are waiting for the political situation in the country to change and stabilize in order to re-enter the Serbian market. The *total number of patent applications* by domestic and foreign authors together in the observed period from 1921 to 2023 follows the behaviour of foreign inventors, which is a consequence of a significantly higher number of patent applications by foreign authors compared to the number of applications by domestic authors. Hence, everything that was stated in the discussion of patenting by foreign authors, mostly applies to the overall patent activity in Serbia.

3. CONCLUSION

In the aforementioned paper from 1998, the author discusses the connection between changes in patent activity and political decisions, that is, laws and by-laws regulating the governance of science and research in the state, which greatly influenced the intensity of patenting [Kutlaca, 1998]. An additional analysis is provided here for the additional period covered by this paper, i.e. for the years from 1995 to 2023. In that period, the following critical periods are significant, which are reflected in Fig. 2 in a large change (mainly decline) in the number of patent applications by domestic authors: (1) The first turning point is precisely 1995-1996, because the end of the wars in the former Yugoslavia is an excuse for the end of the state's support for domestic inventive and innovative efforts, since with the lifting of sanctions, the missing technologies can be bought abroad; (2) The second turning point is 2000-2001, because with the change of regime in Serbia, new perspectives of development based on own knowledge are opened; (3) The third breakthrough period will be 2010-2011, with the beginning of the new project cycle of financing scientific research projects, in which the main emphasis is placed on the publication of articles in journals registered in the WoS and Scopus databases. The laws regulating science and innovation were changed, with the formal recognition of the importance of

patenting, but the mentioned publication, as the main condition for advancement in the academic and scientific career, completely prevailed in the activities of the higher education and scientific community; (4) The final collapse of patent activity began with the corona virus epidemic in 2019, with negative effects lasting until the end of the observed period.

Due to length limitations, the paper presents only a few fragments of the analysis provided by patent statistics for 103 years of patent activity in Serbia. The rich information base represents the basis for a better understanding of the process of building innovation capacities and creating a national innovation system, within and according to the rules of knowledge-based development in the 21st century.

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